

Viable System Verilog Assertions(SVA) Praxis in AMBA AHB-Lite Protocol Design

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Abstract: Digital integrated circuit design entanglement has been far reaching since the demonstration by Kilby in 1958. In this day and age system on chip (SoC) design verification accommodates billion, more specifically trillion transistors designs came into existence due to artificial intelligence (AI) designs. The expertise designers tried to ramp up design process by using effective EDA tools, still the time wheel moves in a recursive process. In order to accelerate the time wheel of design process, a specified design methodology is needed for every design. The overview of various design methodologies followed in the market now a days. Emulation performance by using a veloce platform in BFM mode on AHB-Lite transmissions. Simulation by using software EDA tools is slow going on the wheel of design when we go for higher abstraction. Accelerated simulation and emulation using hardware is costly in contrast with software simulation. Prototyping is expedient. Formal verification and intelligent software simulations are frail. The possibility of selection between various hardware engines becomes ravelled. It develops into a perspicuous amalgamation of engines which will assist design verification teams to be triumphant. In this design combination of hardware accelerated simulator as a combination of emulator used to accelerate the time wheel by using ARM AMBA AHB-Lite protocol as a design.

Keywords: AMBA, AHB LITE, Simulation, Emulation, Assertions

I. INTRODUCTION

In this day and age many new vendors begin to develop their own digital IC intellectual property. One of those is on ARM and each vendor comes up with the needed solution to integrate their electronic devices. These intellectual properties evolve with the help of electronic design automation (EDA) tools in order to pull off the design performance and other tradeoffs such as area, power, and design time. The EDA tools routed by scripting algorithms developed by the design engineers and they self-executing many parts of the design verification flow. So the design verification teams are more with hands on experience make design verification time wheel less and time to market is fast.

The ARM AHB-Lite protocol taken from ARM site modified according to the design requirements and make sure that after modified design works properly and it had the same operation

Revised Manuscript Received on July 05, 2020.

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states that is integrated in ARM IP's. Detailed evaluation of design verification methodologies in market and comparison of methodologies, simulation tools of various vendors. Emulation platform working nature on SoC design SVA (System Verilog Assertions) usage in UVM Environment DUT

II. AHB LITE PROTOCOL

AHB-Lite system can be single master multiple slave as shown in fig.1. Or multi-layer AHB system in which only one AHB master is used. AHB-Lite is an extension of AHB protocol and deliberately useful in system where only need a single bus master.

Fig.1. AHB-Lite system

Fig.2. shows AHB-Lite protocol architecture which consists of single master module and three slave modules in conjunction with the bus interconnection by using decoder and multiplexer.

operation:

when read or write transfer initiated by either master or slave by using address, control signals. those are communicate with decoder to obtain address and direction, size of the transfer. Transfers can be incrementing, wrapping, undefined length, burst transfers

the transaction consists of two operation phases which are Address transaction phase and Data transaction phase the write data bus operation initiated by master and written up in slave. read data bus initiated by slave and reads data from master.

HREADY signal used to develop wait states and slave has more time to sample data.

Fig.2. AHB LITE PROTOCOL ARCHITECTURE Slave

Fig.3. shows AHB Lite slave Top Module AHB Lite slave uses HSELx signal generated by decoded to response the bus transactions controlled master in the protocol. Slave proffer Response either Success ,failure, or waiting transfers

Fig.3. AHB LITE SLAVE TOP

III. ENVIRONMENT

Master: is written/programmed using a Bus Functional Model Approach (not Synthesizable)

-It contains a host of tasks –read, write-that encompass the way the DUT is used.

-By calling those tasks a read or a write would occur on the bus/interface of the DUT

Slave: number of memory modules used in design is parameterized. slave is a RAM, simple memory module.

Monitor: The Current Transactions developed by assertions monitored by using this module and also checks the bus traffic signals.

Interface: Slave MODPORT provide a proper lookup for the slave.

Fig.4.shows SV design verification environment used in simulation and emulation and all the AHB Lite bus signals described in it

Fig.4. SYSTEM VERILOG ENVIRONMENT

IV. VERIFICATION PLAN AND TEST CASES

```

property error_check;
@ (posedge Bus.HCLK) disable iff (Bus.HTRANS == BUSY || Bus.HTRANS == IDLE)
(Bus.HADDR > ((2**10)* NoOfSlaves)) -> (Bus.HRESP == 1'b1);
endproperty
property read_only_error_check;
@ (posedge Bus.HCLK) disable iff ( Bus.HADDR[9:0] > 9'd3)
(Bus.HWRITE == 1'b1) | => (Bus.HRESP == 1);
endproperty
property basic_write;
@ (posedge Bus.HCLK) disable iff ((Bus.HTRANS==IDLE || Bus.HTRANS==BUSY) && Bus.HBURST>0)
$rose(Bus.HWRITE) | => Bus.HREADY;
endproperty.

```

TEST CASES

```

InterfaceInstance.burst_write (32'd5,4,0, data_burst);
#20;
InterfaceInstance.burst_read (32'd5,4,0,
data_burst_read);
#20;
`ifdef DEBUG
$display ("DATA - 0 BUSY - BURST4 = %d, %d, %d,
%d\n", data_burst_read[0], data_burst_read[1],
data_burst_read[2], data_burst_read[3] );
`endif
InterfaceInstance.burst_write (32'd10,8,0, data_burst);
#20;
InterfaceInstance.burst_read (32'd10,8,0,
data_burst_read);
#20;
`ifdef DEBUG
$display ("DATA - 0 BUSY - BURST8 = %d, %d, %d,
%d, %d, %d, %d, %d", data_burst_read[0],
data_burst_read[1], data_burst_read[2], data_burst_read[3],
data_burst_read[4], data_burst_read[5], data_burst_read[6],
data_burst_read[7] );
`endif
InterfaceInstance.burst_write (32'd25,16,0,
data_burst);
#20;

```



```

InterfaceInstance.burst_read (32'd25,16,0,
data_burst_read);
#20;
`ifdef DEBUG
$display ("DATA - 0 BUSY - BURST16 = %d, %d, %d,
%d, %d, %d, %d, %d, %d, %d, %d, %d, %d, %d",
data_burst_read[0], data_burst_read[1], data_burst_read[2],
data_burst_read[3], data_burst_read[4], data_burst_read[5],
data_burst_read[6], data_burst_read[7],
data_burst_read[8], data_burst_read[9],
data_burst_read[10], data_burst_read[11],
data_burst_read[12], data_burst_read[13],
data_burst_read[14], data_burst_read[15]);
`endif
    
```

V. RESULTS

ASEERTION SCOREBOARD WITHOUT ERRORS

----- ASSERTION SCOREBOARD -----			
TYPE OF CHECK	TOTAL COUNT	PASS COUNT	FAIL COUNT
error check	10	10	0
read only error check	6	6	0
basic write error	34	34	0
basic read error check	20	20	0
basic burst write check	32	32	0
basic burst read check	36	36	0
MBREADY check	12	12	0
busy to sequential check	35	35	0
Sequential wait check	11	11	0
bursts count check4	10	10	0
bursts count check8	10	10	0
bursts count check16	12	12	0
address change4	13	13	0
address change8	25	25	0
address change16	24	24	0

ASEERTION SCOREBOARD WITH ERRORS

----- ASSERTION SCOREBOARD -----			
TYPE OF CHECK	TOTAL COUNT	PASS COUNT	FAIL COUNT
error check	96	15	81
read only error check	11	9	2
basic write error	23	23	0
basic read error check	20	20	0
basic burst write check	21	21	0
basic burst read check	36	36	0
MBREADY check	12	12	0
busy to sequential check	19	19	0
Sequential wait check	122	111	11
bursts count check4	10	10	0
bursts count check8	10	10	0
bursts count check16	12	12	0
address change4	13	13	0
address change8	25	25	0
address change16	24	24	0

Emulation -veloce

```

-----
First Slave operations
-----
Basic operations:
-----
Address:000003e4      DataWritten:39944c90      Data Read:39944c90      ---- PASS
Address:00000257      DataWritten:684b2ef0      Data Read:684b2ef0      ---- PASS
Address:0000003d      DataWritten:36c11d55      Data Read:36c11d55      ---- PASS
Address:000001b4      DataWritten:9e39f4a3      Data Read:9e39f4a3      ---- PASS
Address:000003a2      DataWritten:d923ad20      Data Read:d923ad20      ---- PASS
Address:000000b7      DataWritten:2856744e      Data Read:2856744e      ---- PASS
Address:000003e9      DataWritten:649a607d      Data Read:649a607d      ---- PASS
Address:000002bd      DataWritten:b5a9a03b      Data Read:b5a9a03b      ---- PASS
Address:00000257      DataWritten:e1da356c      Data Read:e1da356c      ---- PASS
Address:000002b1      DataWritten:afd15eef      Data Read:afd15eef      ---- PASS
-----
First Slave Burst operations
-----
-----
FAIL
Address:00000006      Data written:0000003b      Data Read:0000003d
Address:00000007      Data written:0000003d      Data Read:0000003f
Address:00000008      Data written:0000003f      Data Read:00000041
Address:00000009      Data written:00000041      Data Read:0000003b
    
```

```

-----
Second Slave operations
-----
Address:000005bd      DataWritten:6f424c03      Data Read:6f424c03      ---- PASS
Address:00000692      DataWritten:6281acc4      Data Read:6281acc4      ---- PASS
Address:00000447      DataWritten:bbac35c3      Data Read:bbac35c3      ---- PASS
Address:00000661      DataWritten:d5579d1b      Data Read:d5579d1b      ---- PASS
Address:000005cf      DataWritten:524ddf99      Data Read:524ddf99      ---- PASS
Address:00000787      DataWritten:975e6523      Data Read:975e6523      ---- PASS
Address:00000468      DataWritten:93e2db7f      Data Read:93e2db7f      ---- PASS
Address:0000058d      DataWritten:0f4f4764      Data Read:0f4f4764      ---- PASS
Address:000007a1      DataWritten:af224f5b      Data Read:af224f5b      ---- PASS
Address:00000748      DataWritten:713f883f      Data Read:713f883f      ---- PASS
-----
Burst operations on Slave 2
-----
FAIL
Address:00000706      Data written:0000003b      Data Read:0000003d
Address:00000707      Data written:0000003d      Data Read:0000003f
Address:00000708      Data written:0000003f      Data Read:00000041
Address:00000709      Data written:00000041      Data Read:0000003b
    
```

```

*****END OF SIMULATION*****
-----
Basic Reads on Slave 1:      10
Basic Writes on Slave 1:     10
Basic Reads on Slave 2:     10
Basic Writes on Slave 2:     10
Pass count:                  20
Fail count:                   0
-----
Burst Reads on Slave 1:     1
Burst Writes on Slave 1:    1
Burst Reads on Slave 2:     1
Burst Writes on Slave 2:    1
Pass count:                  0
Fail count:                   2
    
```

VI. CONCLUSIONS

the initial functionality defining RTL code written from AHB lite specifications taken from ARM documentation. which is exhaustively created test bench environment simulated by using Questasim tool.

design verification issues rapidly increases day by day due to radically increasing in gate count and functionalities . more than 75% time , resources and endeavor takes in detecting bugs in interconnection on SoC chipsets is boundless problem.

simulation and emulation engines combination is unique and SV methodologies proffer accelerated performance ,flexible design, scalability in design area. these methods support real test environment for the design under test (DUT).By wrapping the emulation DUT platform via intelligent interfaces with components enables high speed in design verification.

the systems had high level abstractions can be debugged easily by co emulation constructed test bench. the design verification teams moves to strategic development to accelerate the design performance and time to market

An acceleration ready frame work describes benefits in yielding higher gain over pure simulation and significant decrease in development time for emulation. Users will be able to write block level SV environment that can be uses directly in emulation. this approach will be a solution in getting SoC design verification in shorter times for block, subsystem, system level.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

in the day and age SoC designs are high level abstraction based with innumerable functionalities. to verify SoC deign the teams required more and correlation between each team is mandatory.

If we take a simulator as the baseline, emulation, acceleration and prototyping cam all run faster than a simulator, but the speed-up is dependent on many factors AI SoC Development engineers grasp the design verification environment which will reduce the design services time wheel to come into market .while generating these new generation IP's and soc chipsets .which are highly built in advantages over currently used IP's and soc chipsets

design verification grasp by AI technology makes accelerate the design time and availability in market , which will provide extra time to design teams to make clear cut design features.

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